

Three-Dimensional Interlaminar Stress Distribution in Symmetric Composite Laminate

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ABSTRACT

Interlamina equivalent stress distributed in symmetrically laminated composites with finite dimensions, especially both edge effect near the traction free edges and gripping effect at the clamping ends under uniform axial extension are analysed by Finite Element Method. For simplicity, the laminate is modeled as a set of anisotropic plane elements separated by homogeneous prismatic joint elements. The adhesive stress distribution in macroscopic interface corresponds well with conventional approximation regarding to orthodox and uniform lamination. The singularity of stress state neighbouring to the traction free edges is emphasised by the non-uniformity of fibre density in the lamina.

INTRODUCTION

Compared with homogeneous materials, unnegligible-sized interfaces exist in laminated composites. Those interfaces can be classified as microscopic surfaces in lamina and macroscopic in laminate, that are, in general, called ply-interface. An accurate evaluation of stresses distributed in those boundary layers will help us to better understand the delamination process of composites.

The problem of a finite width, symmetrically laminated composite under uniaxial stretch has been investigated supposing a linear elastic and in-plane stress (1, 2). Previous investigations suggest a possibility of stress singularity at the free edge (3, 4). However, the gripping effect near the clamping end and the material non-linearity caused by the occurrence of microscopic cracks or the non-uniformity of fibre density are neglected.

In this paper, interlamina equivalent stress distributed in symmetrically laminated glass/epoxy composite with finite dimensions, especially both edge effect and gripping effect for the stress under uniaxial extension stress are analysed by elastic-plastic Finite Element Method. Three dimensional prismatic joint element is applied for the modeling of ply-interfaces, since the thickness is negligibly small. Also, the lamina and microscopic interfaces, such as the resin matrix situated between adjacent reinforcements or the non-uniformly of fibre density, are idealised by triangular element in-plane stress. The propriety of idealisation is verified by comparing the numerical and experimental results concerned with strain distribution in top face, as the measurement of interlamina stress is con-

sidered to be difficult in practice. Photo-elasticity by a birefringent coating method is used in this experiment.

LAMINATION MODEL AND FUNDAMENTAL EQUATIONS

To comprehend the piled up construction, the cross section of ($0^\circ/90^\circ$)s laminate is observed by microscope. As shown in Fig. 1, the thickness of adhesive layer situated in mid-surface is negligibly paler than that of another due to lay-up symmetry. Reflecting the above result, the ($+\theta^\circ/-\theta^\circ$)s laminate is modeled by employing triangular and prismatic elements. Each anisotropic layer is assumed to be under generalised plane stress. Fig. 2 illustrates the aspect of modeling. The angle of fibre orientation against Y-direction is defined as $+\theta^\circ$ on the right.

The principle of virtual displacement (5) can be expressed for each constituent element at any equilibrium condition. The stress boundaries at the traction free edges is not taken into account in this particular problem.

$$\int_V (\sigma_{ij} + \Delta\sigma_{ij}) \delta(\Delta E_{ij}) dv = \int_S (T_i + \Delta T_i) \delta(\Delta u_i) ds. \quad (1)$$

Replacing the stiffness drop depending on the occurrence of microfracture with a material non-linearity problem (6), the following constitutive equation is introduced.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl} \Delta E_{kl}, \quad C_{ijkl} = C_{ijkl}^{(e)} \quad (\bar{\sigma} \leq \sigma_r), \\ C_{ijkl} &= C_{ijkl}^{(p)} \quad (\bar{\sigma} > \sigma_r). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

C_{ijkl} represents the orthotropically elastic-plastic anisotropic stiffness coefficients. Its change depends upon n-power law (7). The symbols $\bar{\sigma}$ and σ_r indicate the equivalent and the yielding stress respectively. Hill's criterion \bar{y} (8) is applied to plastic potential to express the rotational change of σ_y in X-Y plane.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}^2 &= 3/2 \{ F + G + H \} \{ F(\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + G(\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 + H(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 \\ &+ 2L\tau_{yz}^2 + 2N\tau_{zx}^2 + 2M\tau_{xy}^2 \}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where F, G, H, L, M, N are the parameter to control the degree of anisotropy and X, Y and Z indicate the orthotropic material axis. Introducing Eq. (2) into Eq. (1), Eq. (1) yield to

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta(\Delta\eta_{ij}) dv + \int_V \Delta\epsilon_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta\epsilon_{ij}) dv + \int_V \{ \Delta\epsilon_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta\eta_{ij}) \\ &+ \Delta\eta_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta\epsilon_{ij}) + \Delta\eta_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta\eta_{ij}) \} dv \\ &= \int_S \Delta T_i \delta(\Delta u_i) ds + \{ \int_S T_i \delta(\Delta u_i) ds - \int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta(\Delta\epsilon_{ij}) dv \}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$\Delta\epsilon_{ij}$ and $\Delta\eta_{ij}$ show the linear and non-linear strain component respectively. And each of them can be written by the increment of element displacement $\Delta u_k^{(e)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\epsilon_{ij} &= (\Delta u_{i,j}^{(e)} + \Delta u_{j,i}^{(e)})/2, \\ \Delta\eta_{ij} &= (\Delta u_{k,i}^{(e)} + \Delta u_{k,j}^{(e)})/2, \quad k = x, y, z. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) and expressing $\Delta u_k^{(e)}$ by shape function ϕ_{ki} and the nodal displacement $\Delta r_i^{(e)}$ as shown in Eq. (6), the element equilibrium equation can be derived.

$$\Delta u_k^{(e)} = \phi_{ki} \Delta r_i^{(e)}. \quad (6)$$

$$(K_{\sigma_{ij}}^{(e)} + K_{Eij}^{(e)} + K_{Lij}^{(e)}) \Delta r_j^{(e)} = \Delta f_i^{(e)}, \quad (7)$$

where the suffix (e) denotes the element number. For example, the linear component of element stiffness $K_{Eij}^{(e)}$ for triangular element can be written as follows.

$$K_{Eij}^{(e)} = 1/4 \int_v (\phi_{ki,l} + \phi_{li,k}) C_{klmn} (\phi_{mj,n} + \phi_{nj,m}) dv. \quad (8)$$

Supposing the adhesive stress distribution to the z-direction to be trivial, the $K_{Eij}^{(e)}$ for prismatic element (Refer to Fig. 3) yields to

$$K_{Eij}^{(e)} = 1/4 \int_v (\phi_{ki,l} + \phi_{li,k}) \xi_{=0} C_{klmn} (\phi_{mj,n} + \phi_{nj,m}) \xi_{=0} dv. \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, the equilibrium equation in terms of symmetric laminate can be derived by superposing the element equation into the whole constituent element.

ANISOTROPIC PARAMETERS

Unidirectionally reinforced plastics show a typical orthotropy as shown in Fig. 4. And the material property is not necessarily linear-elastic by the occurrence of microcracks between reinforcement and matrix. From the Eq. (3), anisotropic parameters required to describe the in-plane stress state can be derived.

$$\begin{aligned} F &= c(1/Y^2 + 1/Z^2 - 1/X^2), & G &= c(1/Z^2 + 1/X^2 - 1/Y^2), \\ H &= c(1/X^2 + 1/Y^2 - 1/Z^2), & N &= c/T^2, & c &= (F + G + H)\bar{\sigma}^2/3, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where X, Y, Z are the yielding stress components in the x, y, z directions respectively, and T is the shear yielding stress in X-Y system. Yielding stresses varied in the X-Y plane can easily be measured by selecting the rotation angle to parameter. On the other hand, the measurement of normal yielding stress Z for the thin plate is difficult in practice. Hence, the incompressibility equation of plastic deformation is introduced.

$$d\epsilon_y^p / d\epsilon_x^p = H/(G + H) = -1/2. \quad (11)$$

Combining Eq. (10) and Eq. (11), the normal yielding stress can be calculated. This way coincides with Tsai's criterion (9) theoretically. Along with the normal stress, the shearing stress in X-Y plane can't be easily obtained. It is well known that the typical four types of configuration in terms of plastic potential are derived by the parameter N (8). From the experimental results shown in Fig. 5, the N can be selected satisfying incidental conditions.

$$G + 2H < N < F + 2H. \quad (12)$$

For example, the comparison between numerical and experimental results is shown in Fig. 5, where $F = 7.99c$, $G = H = 0.0123c$, $N = 0.3c$ ($X = 88.9$ MPa, $Y = Z = 4.9$ MPa).

The derived anisotropic material properties on the lamina are introduced to the stiffness coefficient in the triangular element. The mechanical characteristics of the adhesive layer will be changed practically compared with resin matrix by the production of highly polymerized compound. In the interest of simplicity, the homogeneous material constant of the epoxy is used for joint element.

COMPARISON BETWEEN ANALYTICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Prediction of the equivalent stress distributed in the macroscopic interface is important in determining the failure and the strength of laminate. The above mentioned stress in cross-ply laminate will be influenced by the fibre orientation and the non-uniformity of volume fraction in the lamina. From the previous standpoint, Finite Element analysis is performed especially to estimate the edge and gripping effect on symmetric laminate under uniform axial strain (stretch ratio = 1 %). Variational principal strain in top layer is also observed by a photoelastic coating method in the case of this experiment. The applied material constants of constitutive elements are shown in Table I and the size of specimen is 46*151*1.3 (2b*1*4t, refer to Fig. 2) (mm).

Verification of Modeling

Compared with other reinforcements such as roving with finite width, in-plane characteristics of each lamina strengthened by continuous filaments will be macroscopically homogeneous and orthotropic. The nature of adhesive stress in macroscopic interface for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)$ s laminate is computed from the conventional viewpoint to verify the idealisation of modeling.

The isochromatic fringe patterns for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)$ s laminate is shown in Fig. 6-(a). The variational principal strain in top face varies near the clamping ends. Corresponding numerical result is illustrated in Fig. 6-(b) via contour line. A good agreement with experimental results is found. Namely, the gripping effect restricted near the clamping end can be observed. Fig. 6-(c) shows the distribution of equivalent stress in macroscopic interface. The normal axis denotes the stress concentration factor defined by equivalent stress/uniform extension stress in terms of resin matrix. The adhesive stress approaches to a maximum finite value at the free edges. The result signifies that the debonding on cross-ply laminate with finite dimension is caused by the stress interference neighbouring to the stress boundaries.

As has been shown, the stress state in macroscopic interface varies near the traction-free edges and the clamping ends. Compared with the previous study by Wang and Crossman (4), the stress singularity may not strictly be approximated as the constant strain prismatic element is employed for ply-interface. However an available guideline to protect the macroscopic failure can be established.

Effect of Fibre Density and Orientation on the Interlamina Stress Distribution

The stress state in ply-interface is influenced by the existence of microscopic surfaces in the lamina. By way of emphasising the in-plane boundaries, adjacent reinforcements (preformed tapes) are overlapped systematically. Namely, the diversity of fibre density is arranged regularly in the lamina.

Fig. 7-(a) shows the isochromatic fringe patterns for $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ s laminate with intensified microscopic interface. The gripping effect neighbouring to the clamping ends is reduced to some extent by the coexistence of roughness and fineness of the fibre density. Distribution of variational principal strain in top face and the interlamina equivalent stress are illustrated in Fig. 7-(b) and (c) respectively. Heterogeneous and characteristics distributions are obtained.

Comparison between numerical and experimental results in terms of variational principal strain in top face for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)$ s laminate are shown in Fig. 8-(a) and (b). The degree of non-uniformity is conspicuous, and the shapes of the fringe pattern are influenced by the fibre orientation. Fig. 8-(c) illustrates the distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in the interior region of composites. Stress singularity near the traction-free edges is increased and conspicuous through the emphasised microspheres in the lamina. The result signifies that the occurrence of macroscopic failure in laminate is accelerated by the existence of clear microspheres in the lamina such as the non-uniformity of fibre density.

Compared with another angle-ply laminate, the heterogeneity on isochromatic fringe pattern is conspicuous for $(60^\circ/-60^\circ)$ s as shown in Fig. 9-(a). Corresponding numerical results are shown in Fig. 9-(b) and (c) respectively. The adhesive stress is distributed non-uniformly, influenced by the fibre orientation and the variety of fibre density in the lamina. It is also observed that the gripping effect near the clamping ends is reduced. The same conditions are maintained for $(90^\circ/0^\circ)$ s laminate including strengthened microscopic interface. The results are shown in Fig. 10. Similarly to $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ s laminate, the nature of stress distribution in adhesive layer depends mainly upon the characteristics of the weakest lamina against deformation.

It is made clear that the stress distribution in the interior region of the laminate shows an entirely different nature because of the non-uniformity of fibre density in the lamina. The gripping effect neighbouring to the clamping ends is also reduced. On the other hand, the stress singularity near the free-edge is increased especially for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)$ s laminate.

CONCLUSION

To determine the equivalent stress in macroscopic interface is an available

way to predict the delamination of composites. For this reason, three-dimensional Finite Element analysis is performed to estimate the edge and gripping effect of four layer, symmetric angle-ply laminate under uniaxial extension.

Numerical results that can well approximate the experimental on the distribution of variational principal strain in top layer are observed. The distribution of an equivalent stress in adhesive layer shows an essentially heterogeneous pattern influenced by the fibre orientation and the non-uniformity of the fibre density. Especially for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)$ s laminate with emphasised microscopic interface in the lamina, stress singularity neighbouring to the free-edge is intensified.

In the present problem, the stress component distributed at the finite ends is balanced by the lamination symmetry, although the idealisation presented in this paper might be available for a non-symmetry problem such as the out-plane coupling caused by the thermal residual stresses.

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Table I Material constants of constituent element

	Young's Modulus E_x (GPa)	Young's Modulus E_y (GPa)	Shearing Modulus G_{xy} (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio ν_{xy} (—)	Thickness t (mm)	Yielding Stress σ_y (MPa)
Triangular Element	12.6	3.07	1.47	0.30	0.30	6.0
Prismatic Element	3.40		1.30	0.35	0.05	—

Fig. 1 Cross section of the $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ s laminate

Fig. 2 Illustration of modeling on symmetric composite laminate

Fig. 3 Prismatic joint element

Fig. 4 Non-linear and orthotropic stress to strain relationship

Fig. 5 Relation between tensile yielding stress and rotation angle

(a) Isochromatic fringe patterns ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max} = 1.96\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min} = 0.84\%$) (b) Distribution of variational principal strain in top face ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max} = 2.02\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min} = 0.81\%$) (c) Distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in macroscopic interface

Fig. 6 Comparison between numerical and experimental results for (30°/-30°)s laminate with uniform fibre density

(a) Isochromatic fringe patterns ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.12\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.56\%$) (b) Distribution of variational principal strain in top face ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.17\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.96\%$) (c) Distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in macroscopic interface

Fig. 7 Comparison between numerical and experimental results for $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate with emphasised microscopic interface

(a) Isochromatic fringe patterns ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.68\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.56\%$) (b) Distribution of variational principal strain in top face ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=2.12\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.77\%$) (c) Distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in macroscopic interface

Fig. 8 Comparison between numerical and experimental results for $(30^\circ/-30^\circ)_s$ laminate with emphasised microscopic interface

(a) Isochromatic fringe patterns ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.40\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.84\%$) (b) Distribution of variational principal strain in top face ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.52\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.63\%$) (c) Distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in macroscopic interface

Fig. 9 Comparison between numerical and experimental results for $(60^\circ/-60^\circ)_s$ laminate with emphasised microscopic interface

(a) Isochromatic fringe patterns ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.12\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.56\%$) (b) Distribution of variational principal strain in top face ($\Delta\epsilon_{\max}=1.17\%$, $\Delta\epsilon_{\min}=0.96\%$) (c) Distribution of interlamina equivalent stress in macroscopic interface

Fig. 10 Comparison between numerical and experimental results for $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_s$ laminate with emphasised microscopic interface